

COMPETENCE IN THE PROCESS OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The main focus of the article is on the essence of the concepts of "competence", "professional competence", aspects of the specialist's competence, classifications, groups of professional competences and the main ways and means of their development.

The globalization of the economy, the formation of the information society in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the integration of its higher education system on a global scale have given our pedagogical sciences the task of adapting the field of traditional Uzbek science to the educational system based on the national characteristics of the pedagogical concepts accepted in the world puts in particular, the improvement of the knowledge paradigm of education from the point of view of the competence approach shows the appropriateness of the purpose.

The specialist's competence includes the following aspects:

- intellectual - is the ability to acquire knowledge, the ability of a person to acquire and use knowledge and experience, to be able to behave rationally in problematic situations, to mutually adjust the goals, tasks, standards of the activities to be carried out expresses readiness to know and perform them effectively;
- high-level mastery of qualifications and skills, work techniques and technologies for practical - retransformation activities;
- awareness of values - relying on the superiority of cultural and spiritual values.

The intellectual abilities of a person are seen in the intellectual qualities that a person has, to these qualities we can include the competence of a person as an inseparable unit of creativity, initiative, intellectual originality of mind, knowledge acquisition and motivational factors. Professional creativity is the process of creating new ideas and implementing them in a specific activity. The skills of self-management, ability to freely manage one's intellectual activity, ability to plan accordingly, ability to independently solve the tasks of acquiring knowledge are important in creative work.

An intellectual person should have the following qualities: a) possession of various systematic knowledge; b) qualified; c) quickness, ability to use knowledge quickly in necessary situations; g) forms and means of putting theoretical rules into practice;

d) distinguish basic elements.

In intellectual competence, the "erudite culture" is emphasized, which means that the activity of acquiring knowledge prevails in a person, and he strives to accumulate knowledge to the maximum extent. But, according to A. Mol, "it is necessary to distinguish between two types of erudition: simply expanding the field of cultural worldview, in other words, increasing the number of elements in the mind's treasury, on the one hand, and the social or individual organism, which is determined by the thickness and depth of the layer of associations. The information that is built up by the mind in the process of thinking and then stored in the memory is on the other side.

Professional initiative is manifested as a person's desire to search for new information, to raise one or another idea, to master other areas of activity, to deviate from the known framework and engage in intellectual activity that is not stimulated from the outside. Intellectual initiative should be considered as a holistic feature.

When considering the problems of modernization of education, the term "professional competence" is widely used to define requirements for graduates of higher education institutions.

T. Yu. Bazarov considers the category of "professional competence" to be a specialist's readiness and ability to make effective decisions in the course of his professional activities. Professional competence is "in general, a whole, integrated set of knowledge, skills and experience, as well as personal qualities, which allows a person to effectively design and implement his professional activities in relation to the environment."

Considering professional competencies, most researchers⁶ emphasize the following:

1) simple (basic) competencies (formed on the basis of knowledge, skills and abilities that are manifested in certain types of activity and can be easily strengthened);

2) basic competencies are very difficult to consider and measure, they are manifested in all types of activity, in all relationships of a person with the environment, reflect the spiritual world of a person and the content of his activity.

In some studies, there are different definitions: standard competencies - without them, the normal functioning of a person or an organization is impossible; basic competencies - raise them to higher ranks in the social-economic market compared to their peers and ensure their competitiveness; leading competencies are "creating" the future, which is manifested in innovation, creativity, forward thinking, compromise.

As a result of observing the activities of the most effective pedagogues and modeling the future needs, a number of types of competence based on the three main links of the pedagogue's activity and personality have been identified: "to know, to perform, to have". Since then, the impact of the teacher's personal qualities on his professional competence has been recognized by all researchers. Development of competence approaches to professional training of teachers I.L. Zimnyaya made a great contribution. He divided all qualities of a pedagogue into objective and subjective qualities: objective qualities are the teacher's level of knowledge of his subject, mastery of the methodology of the subject and the depth of his scientific knowledge, mastery of general didactic and specific methodical principles, child psychology good knowledge and full acceptance of its characteristics; subjective: pedagogical art, pedagogical talent, creativity, etc.

N.I. When studying the professional competence of a pedagogue, Almazova grouped the skills and personal qualities of a pedagogue that allow to increase the effectiveness of teaching and made the following conclusion: "The professional competence of a pedagogue is the work of a pedagogue, in which pedagogical activity and pedagogical communication are sufficiently is carried out at a high level, the personality of the teacher is revealed, good results are achieved in teaching and educating students".

The content of the professional and personal competence of the teacher of the 21st century T.E. Isaeva described and explained in detail. The author grouped competencies as follows: flexible-modern competencies; social competences; social and organizational competencies; professional (in special subjects and special methodology) competencies - knowledge, skills, teaching methods selected based on the specific characteristics of the taught subject and in accordance with the unique pedagogical system of the teacher, a set of methods of transfer of professional-corporate experience; communicative competences that ensure the preservation of a person's "identity" in any conditions based on values.

Modern researchers pay great attention to the classification of the competence of a graduate of higher education institutions. For example, T.E. Isaeva distinguishes the following basic competencies in her "Basic Competencies of the 21st Century Manager" course: strategic; social; functional; management; Just as it is not possible to describe the main aspects of the emergence of the concepts of "competence" and "competence" in modern pedagogical practice, it is not possible to give a detailed analysis of their classification within the framework of this article. However, it is important to define the main direction:

a) clarification of the content of competence recognized as the most important for graduates of higher education institutions; b) the main ways and means of developing professional competence in modern higher education, which can include the following:

- the variety of problem-situational tasks offered for selection, taking into account the level of professional orientation, professional orientation and preparation, individual characteristics, personal interests and opportunities of students (variability according to the level of complexity and independence);
- development of students' independence based on harmonizing collective (group of students) and individual forms of work performance;
- encourage students to self-monitor and analyze the work they have done and the level of professional training;
- broad involvement of students in various forms of creative activity and self-management;
- active participation of students in spiritual and cultural events organized on the scale of the republic and higher educational institution.

Only if the institution of higher education fulfills the role of an intermediary between the student and the national and universal principles of spiritual and cultural values, not as a source of information, first of all, it includes the student's activities of personal interest, creativity, communication, study and knowledge acquisition. the educational process as a life activity, and secondly, as a method of mastering the current state and historical development of culture, can become real conditions for the development of the specialist's professional competence.

The concepts of "competence" and "competence" have not only taken a solid place in pedagogical sciences, but are also being studied more and more deeply by a wide range of pedagogues-practitioners. In the study of professional competence, the following groups of professional competences are considered necessary for the formation of professional competence of future teachers:

- diagnostic - the ability to acquire new knowledge about production, to generalize and systematize one's own personal experience and the experience of the pioneers and innovators of production;

- design - creation of technical and technological systems, sewing objects, current and prospective planning of professional activities, design of a management and control system of technological processes;

- organization - being able to put engineering ideas into practice, being able to lead a team;

- technological - to be able to organize technological processes, to be able to read drawings and technological maps, to be able to determine the possibilities and conditions necessary for the performance of assigned tasks, technical specifications of equipment and devices;

- construction - to be able to perform calculation and graphic work on the preparation of products, to be able to perform sketches and drawings, to be able to establish a technological process in accordance with technical conditions, to be able to determine a system of actions for eliminating malfunctions.

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